

MOTIVATION PROBLEMS OF CORRECTIVE MOTOR-PLAY ACTIVITY OF CHILDREN WITH PSYCHOMOTOR DISORDERS AND POSSIBLE WAYS OF THEIR SOLUTION

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Abstract

The article analyzes one of the main problems of physical rehabilitation of children with psychomotor disorders – the problem of motivation in corrective motor activity. This determined the *aim* – to determine the main directions of the motivational sphere formation in the process of correctional play activity of children with psychomotor disorders.

The following research *methods* were used: the method of analysis, which made it possible to identify the main characteristics and types of motivational support of children for various types of activity; the method of pedagogical observations and the method of synthesis revealed the powerful method of motivating – theatricalization of the correctional process using physical education.

The research *results* were expressed in the definition of the concepts: motive, motivational field, motivational impulse, which are the components of the concept of motivation, the variety of which is defined in four types.

There were made following *conclusions*:

1. The motivation of corrective motor-play activity is based on the unconscious influences of the unconscious, caused by the external use by the teacher of the corresponding children's fairy-tale archetypes and the emotional experiences, caused by them.
2. One of the main methods of increasing motivation is the use of the possibilities of pedagogical “drama” in the form of a method of dosed dramatization of the motor-game plot of a remedial lesson, which should be considered as a physical culture fairy tale.
3. For the implementation of effective dramatic motivation, it is necessary to provide points of dramatization of different influence strength.

Keywords: motivation, psychomotor disorders, children, motor-play activity, correction, dosed dramatization.

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1. Introduction

It is well known, that one of the main correcting problems of the development of children with mental and motor disorders is the problem of motivating their corrective motor activity [1, 2]. Scientists proposed a schematic diagram of the pathological mechanism of secondary motor disorders in children with primary mental retardation based on motor activity motivation reduction (**Fig. 1**).

Despite numerous studies of the problem of increasing motivation in children with psychomotor disorders [3, 4], the details of the main directions in this direction are not sufficiently disclosed.

Fig. 1. Pathological mechanism of the occurrence of secondary motor disorders based on lack of motivation in children with mental retardation

The study aims to determine the main directions of the motivational sphere formation in the process of correctional play activity of children with psychomotor disorders.

2. Research methods

The analysis method made it possible to identify the main characteristics and types of motivational support of children for various types of activity. The method of pedagogical observations and the method of synthesis revealed theatricalization of the correctional process using physical education as one of the most powerful methods of motivating children of early and preschool age.

3. Results and discussions

In general terms, motivation (from the French “motifver” – to condition) can be considered as a system of motives that causes a person’s activity and determines its direction. It makes sense to consider the concept of *motivation for educational and pedagogical activities* in more detail.

According to some authors [2], the purposeful formation of motivation for learning activity among students is extremely important and necessary. Based on the determining motivation value for educational activity, the principle of motivational support of the educational process was formulated.

Motive is one of the key concepts of the psychological theory of activity, which was developed by the leading Soviet psychologists A. N. Leontiev and S. L. Rubinstein. Within the framework of this theory, the simplest definition of a motive is the following: “**A motive is an objectified need**” [5]. The motive is often confused with the need and the goal, but the need is an unconscious desire to eliminate discomfort, and the goal is the result of conscious goal-setting. The motive resolves this dual contradiction between the unconscious and the planned, purposeful. That scientist wrote that “it is necessary for teaching to enter life so that it has vital meaning for the student. Even in teaching ordinary motor skills, this is also true.”

Psychology defines **motivation** as *conscious or unconscious mental factors that induce an individual to perform certain actions and determine their direction and goals*. The term «motivation» is used in all areas of psychology that investigate the causes and mechanisms of purposeful human behaviour. Thus, motivation is made up of impulses that cause a person’s activity and determine the direction of this activity. The aspect of “unconscious mental factors” seems to be very interesting for us, since it is the unconscious, i.e. the unconscious always harbours a huge energy potential. Learning to use this hidden and very powerful potential of unconscious motives is the most urgent direction for researching the problems of motivation in children of early and preschool age with psychomotor disorders.

From the standpoint of pedagogy, **learning motivation** is a general name for *processes, methods, and means of encouraging students (children) to productive cognitive activity, to actively master the content of education*. We are impressed by the position of authors [4], who comprehensively consider this problem, from two opposite sides of educational activity participants: teachers and children. They believe that both teachers (motivation for learning, their attitude to professional duties) and children (motivation for learning, internal self-motivation (**Fig. 2**) hold the images of motivation in their hands. Researchers believe that: “Motivation is the leading factor, regulating the activity, behaviour, actions of the individual. Any pedagogical interaction with a student becomes effective only with regard to his/her motivation.”

There can be completely different reasons behind the objectively identical deeds of students. Incentive sources of the same deed can be completely different” [6, 7]. We also propose to consider the problem of motivation in a complex, dualistic manner in the unity of two opposite poles: both from the position of teaching (pedagogical position) and the position of learning (child position). In our opinion, in children of early and preschool age, the conscious motivation of the learning process, for example, one or another corrective motor actions, is not expressed clearly enough and fully. The impulse must come from the outside, and this impulse must be created by the teacher. We can talk about a conditional **motivational field**. Such a field can create any object, with which the child wants to tinker – this phenomenon is described in the *field theory* of Kurt Lewin [8]. A similar field can be created by a free, *dynamic space* according to the

theory of Efimenko N. and Moga N. [9]. However, the strongest motivational field, in our opinion, at this age can only be created by a teacher. The teacher must set the *primary motivational* impulse in the form of the corresponding subject-spatial environment [8, 9], and by creating the necessary **playing field**. In this case, the teacher creates a primary motivational field, after which the child's self-motivation begins to vibrate:

Fig. 2. Learning motivation structure

Motivational field (playing field) = teacher's motivational impulse → child's auto-motivation.

In this regard, it seems very interesting to define motivation as a process of *motivating one-self and others* to activities to achieve personal goals or the goals of an organization. This allows to expand the concept of a motivational field to the following form:

Motivational field (playing field) = teacher's motivational impulse → child's auto-motivation + external motivational impulse of the child (in relation to other children).

Interestingly, Levin K. in the last months of his life began to significantly revise his *concept of motivation*, in order to place less emphasis on the traditional concept of “need” and place more – on such determinants as group membership, personal ability, economic and political resources, social channels, and other factors that are usually not considered in the psychological theory of motivation. In this conceptual approach, we are particularly interested in two dual determinants as *group membership and personal ability*.

Motives have both *quantitative* and *qualitative* characteristics. Quantitative motives can be differentiated based on the «strong-weak» principle. Qualitative characteristics are indicated by their belonging to *internal* or *external* motives. If for a student (child) an activity is significant in itself (for example, satisfying a cognitive need in the learning process), then this is internal motivation. If social factors (for example, prestige, salary, etc.) are the impetus for the activity of the individual, then this is external motivation. Internal and external motives are linked in a certain way. The internal motive acts as an incentive that means that there is a need to carry out an activity,

and the external one (an object, means or external conditions) acts as an incentive that means that it is possible to implement it (the availability of the desired product of activity). At the same time, the internal stimulus is primary, and external objects induce only if there is an internal stimulus. From the above, the following definition can be introduced: *motivation impulse*.

The definition of motivation as a system of interrelated and mutually subordinate motives of a person's activity, consciously determining the line of his/her behaviour, seems to be very productive [10]. This interpretation of the concept makes it possible to see motivation systemically not as a one-time impulse, but as a set of sequential motives, predetermined by the peculiarity of the created pedagogical situation. In this regard, let's remember Yerkes-Dodson law: *the effectiveness of educational activity depends on the strength of motivation - the stronger the motivation for action, the higher the result of the activity! After achieving certain results, a further increase of the motivation strength does not increase the activity efficiency*. Perhaps, to increase the correctively directed motor-play activity of children, it is not necessary to further strengthen the previous motivation but to *change the motive to a new one*.

A certain epistemological "zest" is in the definition of motivation as a set of *persistent motives*, impulses that determine the content, direction and nature of a person's activity. The persistence of motives should be sought in historical memory, in the sphere of the unconscious, in the archetypes of Jung C. [11]. According to the authors, the introduction of children's *archetypal images* into the game plot, inherently associated with ancient, historical archetypes, can significantly increase the motivation of motor corrective activity in children, while releasing a huge resource of unconscious energy and thereby increasing the effectiveness of physical rehabilitation.

There is a widespread belief that internal motivation for learning is the most natural, leading to the best results in the learning process. However, some authors [4] believe that observations in certain life situations, as well as theoretical considerations, do not allow unconditionally to accept this position as axiomatic.

Several researchers [4] believe that the cognitive motive itself contains a "business" motive. Carrying out cognitive activities, the student understands to one degree or another that his/her results can be useful in order to subsequently receive certain benefits in life. Therefore, the absolutization of the cognitive motive as internal concerning the teaching and opposing it to the business motive seems inappropriate.

Note that Rubinstein S. included both of these motive types among the main motives of teaching, arguing that the main motives of conscious teaching, associated with the awareness of its tasks, are natural tendencies to prepare for their future activities and since teaching is world discovering, interest in obtaining knowledge. He wrote that these two types of motives often turn out to be so closely related to each other that it becomes impossible to oppose them. Thus, the business motive is also "internal" in relation to teaching, in contrast to such really external motives as self-affirmation or the receipt of any other benefits, to which the teaching is not directly related [12].

It should be noted, that the auto-motivation of joint educational activities in children of early and preschool age has its own age-related psychophysiological specificity. In the pedagogical literature, there are four types of motivation among preschoolers [3]:

The first type is play motivation – "Help the toy", the child achieves the learning goal by solving the problem of toys. The creation of this motivation is built according to the scheme:

1. You tell that the toys need help and only children can help them.
2. You ask the children if they are willing to help the toy.
3. You propose to teach children to do what the toy requires, then the explanation and demonstration will interest the children.
4. During work, each child should have his/her own character – the ward (toy).
5. The same toy - the tutor assesses the child's work, be sure to praise the child.
6. At the end of the work, it is desirable that the children play with their tutors.

With this motivation, the child acts as an assistant and protector, and it is appropriate to use it to teach various practical skills.

The second type of motivation is helping an adult – "Help me". Here, the motivation for children is communication with an adult, the opportunity to gain approval, as well as an

interest in joint activities that can be done together. The creation of motivation is built according to the scheme:

1. You inform the children that you are going to make something and ask the children to help you.
2. Wondering how they can help you.
3. Each child is given a feasible task.
4. In the end, stress that the result was achieved through joint efforts, that everyone came to it together.

The third type of motivation is “Teach me”. Based on the child’s desire to feel knowledgeable and able. The creation of this motivation is carried out according to the scheme:

1. You inform the children that you are going to do an activity and ask the children to teach you how to do it.
2. You ask if they are willing to help you.
3. Each child is allowed to teach you any business.
4. At the end of the game, each child is given an assessment of his/her actions and must be praised.

The fourth type of motivation is “creating objects with your own hands for yourself.” Based on the inner interest of the child. This motivation encourages children to create objects and crafts for their own use and their loved ones. Children are sincerely proud of their crafts and willingly use them” [6].

The first type of motivation is of particular interest to us since it is associated with the main activity of the preschooler – play. According to T. Kudryavtseva, “...effective methods of influencing the emotional and cognitive sphere of children with developmental disabilities are:

- game situations;
- didactic games, which are associated with the search for specific and generic characteristics of objects;
- game training that contribute to the development of communication skills;
- psycho-gymnastics and relaxation, allowing to relieve muscle spasms” [7].

4. Discussion

Our own long-term experience of working with children with psychomotor disorders allowed us to find one of the most powerful methods of motivating children of early and preschool age – **theatricalization of the correctional process using physical education** [5]. This approach has been practised in our Movement Rehabilitation Center for 30 years and has proven itself in the best possible way. The most appropriate form of correctional physical education was found in the form of a **physical culture fairy tale** for a preschool child. Thus, the lesson from a purely functional, mechanistic (training) turned into a theatrical action with all the ensuing significant play and pedagogical possibilities. First, this refers to the obligatory plot of the correctional physical education lesson. Since any plot implies the presence of certain fairy-tale characters, **imagery** immediately appears in such an activity. Any of the images has a set of biological or personal characteristics that are peculiar to him/her and make him/her special. In this regard, the **plot-role manifestations** of a child with psychomotor disorders are actualized. Theatrical joint motor-play activity of a teacher and children implies an intense **emotionality** of such a correctional lesson. In our opinion, such an emotional background of the lesson should not be uniformly positive – positive emotions should be intelligently alternated with neutral or negative ones. The method of **dosed dramatization of the correctional process** will greatly help the teacher in this. And here we come very close to the problem of increasing motivation since the word “**drama**” in translation from Greek means “**action**”, and active action is possible only if there is a high motivation for its implementation [13].

At the heart of the dosed dramatization of the correctional process, we put the main dual pair of ancient archetypal images – the struggle between Good and Evil. Based on this, negative characters or negative situations are introduced into the plot of the correctional lesson, requiring struggle with the main character (heroes), played by a specific child or a subgroup of children. We can talk about conditional points of dramatization, which must be correctly put in the plot of the upcoming

lesson. There should not be many of them, since the energy and emotional potential of the child is limited. Usually, these are 2-4 situations for 30 minutes. The points of dramatization in terms of the degree of impact can be conditionally divided into *weak, medium and strong*. The weak point of dramatization means the presence in the plot of a not very expressive negative character who, by his/her intentional or unintentional actions, creates some discomfort for our heroes (children). For example, it could be an Annoying Fly. The middle point of dramatization should be attributed to the average negative character who, by his/her actions, interferes with the implementation of the positive plans of children. An example of such a character is the North Wind. The strong point of dramatization implies an expressive negative character who not only interferes with the realization of children positive plot plans, but also encroaches (conditionally) on their property, freedom, health and life. Usually, these are some kind of forest fairy monsters: Leshy, Baba Yaga, Koschei, Vodyanoy, Chudushko Lesnoy, Zmei Gorynych and other modern characters from fairy tales and cartoons [14].

We propose to call this methodological approach of increasing motivation using pedagogical “drama” *dramatic motivation*. And here we are very close to the position of Anokhin P. about “... *the dominant motivation at the moment...*” [1]. When developing the plot of a remedial physical education lesson, the teacher scenarist must introduce the points of dramatization in it so that the weak points go first, then they are strengthened by the middle ones, and only at the end of the lesson should be introduced strong points of dramatization. This option of stimulating motivation can be called *progressive*, and it is the main one in the work. The practice of our corrective activity also tested a variant of *wave-like* motivation, when points of dramatization alternated in the course of the lesson according to the type: weak – medium – weak, medium – strong – medium, weak – medium – strong → weak – medium – strong. A *decreasing* incentive option (strong – medium – weak) showed its insufficient motivational attractiveness [15].

“It is unlikely that anyone would dare to deny that two opposite human states – suffering and satisfaction – are one of the most important results of the evolution of life on earth and that, having joined the system of human social relations, these states have become a powerful engine of progress! ... It should be noted, that in all these cases, behaviour is always built completely adequately to the nature of the emotional factor that arose in response to irritation ... In other words, the study should include an account of the *emotional factor of the reaction*” [1]. The method of dosed dramatization of a correctively directed physical culture lesson provides such opportunities – to vary the emotional state of children depending on the scenario collisions of the motor-game plot!

Prospects for further research. Problems of motivation of corrective motor-play activity in children of early and preschool age with psychomotor disorders are seen in the further study of the possibilities of using archetypal mental structures of the collective unconscious and images of the individual unconscious as a method of stimulating this activity.

6. Conclusions

1. In children of early and preschool age, the motivation of corrective motor-play activity is based not so much on the conscious internal motives of learning, but on the unconscious influences of the unconscious, caused by the external application of the corresponding children’s fairy-tale archetypes and the emotional experiences, caused by them by the teacher.

2. In this regard, the play method of interacting with children is fundamental for children of early and preschool age. One of the main methods of increasing motivation in children with psychomotor disorders is the use of the possibilities of pedagogical “drama” in the form of a method of dosed dramatization of the motor-game plot of a physical education lesson, which should be considered as a physical culture fairy tale, a kind of a dramatic theatrical performance.

3. To implement effective dramatic motivation in the developed plot of the lesson, it is necessary to provide points of dramatization of different strength of influence and arrange them in a certain sequence, the main of which is progressive (weak – medium – strong).

Conflicts of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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